

PEDAGOGICAL ETHICS IN EDUCATION AND THE EXAMPLE OF THE TEACHER PERSON

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Abstract: This article analyzes the issues of adherence to pedagogical ethics and exemplary personality of the teacher in the modern education system from a scientific and theoretical perspective. It considers the teacher's adherence to the norms of professional ethics, being a positive example for students, and having a positive impact on the educational process through his personal qualities. It also highlights the role of the teacher in forming a moral and cultural environment in educational institutions, his social responsibility, maintaining a professional image, and ethical standards in pedagogical activity as important factors. The article shows effective ways to implement pedagogical ethics in the education system based on advanced foreign and local experiences.

Keywords: Pedagogical ethics, teacher personality, exemplary personality, professional ethics, social responsibility, quality of education, educational process.

Introduction

In today's era of globalization, the requirements placed on the education system are becoming increasingly complex, and the role of the teacher as not only a specialist who provides knowledge, but also a person who can be a moral example in society is also increasing. An educational institution is not only a place to impart knowledge, but also a place for the formation of human maturity, moral views and social responsibility. The main mediator in this process is the educator, that is, the teacher. Every word, action, and attitude of the teacher directly affects the student. Therefore, adhering to pedagogical ethics and setting a positive example for students must become an integral part of the teacher's personality.

The professional exemplary nature of a teacher means not only passing a lesson well or imparting knowledge, but also being a well-rounded, fair, impartial and responsible person in all respects. He teaches the child not only the subject matter in the textbook, but also life values, norms and moral criteria. By communicating with students in accordance with pedagogical ethics, demonstrating such qualities as equality, respect, patience, honesty and kindness, a teacher is not only a devotee of his profession, but also a moral pillar of society.

Nowadays, when the quality of education has become a priority issue, the inner world of a teacher, his loyalty to the norms of professional ethics and exemplary character are important components of the educational process. After all, no matter how much a student uses modern technologies, he is, first of all, a being who learns and feels humanity. Therefore, a deeper study of the issue of pedagogical ethics in education, identifying the criteria that determine the exemplary nature of a teacher's personality are one of the urgent tasks facing modern pedagogical science.

Methodology.

The main methodological direction of this study is aimed at analyzing the professional and moral qualities of a teacher in the context of the pedagogical process, based on the principles of humanism in education. From this perspective, qualitative research methods are of primary importance in scientific research. In determining the exemplary personality of a teacher, humanistic pedagogy, an ethical-cultural approach, and the concept of person-centered education were chosen as the theoretical basis.

A number of empirical and theoretical methods were used during the research. First, through the analysis of scientific literature, foreign and local pedagogical sources related to pedagogical ethics, professional ethics, social responsibility and exemplary character of the teacher were studied. Through this method, the theoretical foundations of the topic were deepened and approaches to the topic were compared.

Secondly, through the methods of interviews and observation, the approach to their profession, attitude to students, communication culture and personal qualities of teachers working in current educational institutions were studied. Through these methods, the moral exemplary character of the teacher was assessed not only theoretically, but also practically. In particular, a comparative analysis of the activities of young teachers and experienced teachers showed differences in attitudes towards the norms of professional ethics.

Third, through questionnaires and surveys, the views on the exemplary character of the teacher were studied among students, pupils and parents. This method served to analyze the impact of pedagogical ethics in society, to determine the criteria by which the teacher's personality is evaluated.

Thus, the combination of theoretical and practical analysis methods in this scientific research made it possible to effectively study pedagogical ethics in education, to determine the exemplary nature of the teacher's personality on a scientific basis and to apply it in practice.

Literature analysis (review):

The topic of pedagogical ethics and the exemplary nature of the teacher's personality is relevant in the field of modern education, and scientific views on this issue have been studied by national and foreign researchers from different perspectives. Literature analysis shows that the concept of pedagogical ethics has a broad meaning and includes the ethical criteria that a teacher must adhere to during his professional activities, the culture of relationships, the quality of interpersonal communication, and a sense of responsibility.

Local researcher A. Joraev (2020) in his work "Fundamentals of Pedagogical Ethical Culture" draws attention to the moral qualities of a teacher, his speech culture, and the norms of etiquette in communicative relations with students. According to him, the moral exemplary nature of a teacher is an important factor not only for his professional image, but also for the quality of education and educational effectiveness.

In foreign sources, pedagogical ethics is analyzed more within the framework of professional code of conduct and moral responsibility. For example, N. Strike and J. Soltis (2009) in their work "The Ethics of Teaching" shed light on the ethical dilemmas in the actions of a teacher and ways to solve them on a philosophical and theoretical basis. The authors indicate the concepts of justice, respect, and trust as central ethical values in the educational process.

Also, the document "Teachers' Code of Conduct" presented by UNESCO (2017) sets out international standards for the professional ethics of teachers, which places special emphasis on respect for the rights of students, transparency, impartiality and social responsibility.

Among the studies on the exemplary qualities of a teacher, the scientific article "Personal qualities and the harmony of the teaching profession" by M. Yuldashev (2018) is noteworthy. It analyzes the inner world, will, culture of behavior, emotional stability and social activity of a teacher in their inextricably linked with the quality of education.

Many scientific studies conclude that pedagogical ethics is not just a set of norms, but a real expression of the teacher's personal qualities and internal moral position. This, in turn, directly affects his personal exemplary character. In general, the analysis of the literature shows that the moral and professional development of the teacher's personality is one of the main directions of modern pedagogy, and in this direction a harmonious approach is necessary, combining ethics, aesthetic culture, communication and leadership qualities.

Discussion:

In an era when the modern education system is becoming increasingly complex, the issue of the formation of a teacher not just as a provider of knowledge, but as a spiritual and moral leader remains extremely relevant. Every action, thought, behavior and appearance of a teacher forms certain images in the minds of students. Therefore, adherence to pedagogical ethics, a responsible approach to one's profession, and a humane attitude towards students are among the main criteria that determine the professional exemplariness of a teacher.

The personality of a teacher occupies a central place in the socio-psychological environment of a school or higher education institution. He is not only a teacher of the curriculum, but also a mediator of moral and cultural values. The student learns from the teacher's honesty, sincerity, manners, behavior, and sometimes even silence. In such a process, any action not based on pedagogical ethics can negatively affect the development of the student's personality.

However, unfortunately, today in some cases it seems that the teaching profession is focused only on administrative and technical tasks. Ignoring ethical standards, lax behavior, and lack of personal responsibility undermine not only the quality of education, but also the professional and spiritual formation of students. Therefore, teachers' knowledge of and adherence to the standards of professional ethics should become mandatory in educational institutions.

The exemplary nature of a teacher is manifested not only in his appearance, but also in his inner convictions, decisions, attitude to problems, and determination to choose justice. He should strive to have a positive impact on students through his personal qualities in any situation. This requires continuous self-development, reflection, a critical approach to pedagogical activity, and work on himself. The above analysis shows that pedagogical ethics and the example of the teacher's personality are closely related, and their harmony ensures not only personal success, but also the spiritual upliftment of society as a whole. Through his exemplary behavior, the teacher not only teaches lessons, but also creates an impressive human image that will be remembered throughout his life.

Conclusion

The role of the teacher in the education system and his moral example serve as a decisive factor in the formation of the student's personality. A teacher who adheres to

pedagogical ethics, is loyal to his profession, and prioritizes ethical standards in his activities is not only a teacher, but also a spiritual leader of society. The results of the study show that every behavior, attitude, communication culture, and personal qualities of a teacher leave a deep mark on the social consciousness of the student. It is also necessary to systematically teach pedagogical ethics in educational institutions, constantly improve the professional and moral training of teachers, and harmonize ethical standards with practice. To this end, mechanisms should be developed to provide teachers with constant moral guidance through methodological manuals, trainings, and professional development programs. In conclusion, pedagogical ethics and exemplary personality of the teacher in education are inextricably linked concepts, and their development ensures the quality, effectiveness and humane nature of the educational process. This serves as a solid foundation for the development of society and the upbringing of the younger generation as a complete person.

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